

Raw MALDI-TOF MS Data

The list of mass-to-charge (m/z) peak values obtained from MALDI-TOF MS analyses of *Salmonella* Typhimurium under various experimental conditions (treatment with *Bifidobacterium bifidum*, *Lactiplantibacillus plantarum*, and *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*)

Species	Condition	m/z (Da)
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	595.39593
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	639.42348
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	683.44898
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	727.47763
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	771.50615
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	771.50615
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	815.53255
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	859.56707
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	903.59353
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	947.62218
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	991.6608
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	1035.68395
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	1199.90913
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	1651.16972
<i>Salmonella</i>	+bifidum	1651.16972
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	595.3957
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	639.42294
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	683.4487
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	727.4773
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	771.50641
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	771.50641
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	815.53302
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	859.56614
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	903.59499

<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	947.62191
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	991.66011
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	1035.68333
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	1199.90887
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	1199.90887
<i>Salmonella</i>	+plantarum	1651.16163
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	595.39625
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	639.42281
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	683.44822
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	727.47689
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	771.50588
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	815.53204
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	859.56621
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	903.59387
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	947.62106
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	991.65942
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	1035.68402
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	1199.90974
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	1651.16391
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	1853.24918
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	2597.71785
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	2828.50589
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	3161.16902
<i>Salmonella</i>	+saccharo	3514.32011
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	595.39583
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	639.423
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	683.44873
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	727.47736
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	771.50595

<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	771.50595
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	815.53242
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	859.56583
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	903.59439
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	947.62155
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	991.65964
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	1199.90883
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	1199.90883
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	1651.16585
<i>Salmonella</i>	Control	1651.16585